

DESCRIPTION OF THE FATHERLAND IN THE CREATION OF BAZOR SABIR

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Annotation: Bozor Sabir is considered a lyric poet and left an indelible mark in Tajik literature with his work. His poems are mainly dedicated to Motherland, motherland, nature. In his series of poems dedicated to the theme of the Motherland, the historical view of the lyrical hero occupies a special place. In them, the heroic and tragic pages of the history of the nation and the motherland pass through the feelings and thoughts of the lyrical hero, the dramatic scenes of the life and struggle of the ancestors of the Tajik people and their proud children for freedom. and well-being will appear. The position and position of a person in society, the poet's responsibility to history and humanity, the essence of the author's word in human life, and the goals and tasks form the content of the poems of the Bozor Sabir series. This is the voice of our hearts. This holy place is the qibla of prostration. We drink its water, breathe its pleasant air, its soil and grains are dear to us. The memory of the homeland will never leave us. His name inspires our hearts and our bodies receive new inspiration every moment.

Young people always appreciate their Motherland and strive for its development. One of such people's young men, a powerful child of the people, a powerful and prominent poet Bozor Sabir made a significant contribution to modern Tajik literature with his unique poems.

I understood the homeland without explaining it,

I understand passengers after their goods.

I am bound to him both by step and by pen,

If I lose his gift, I will be lost.

His torn tombs are my eyes,

Ripped tombs are my territory.

Besides, a handful of father soil

I don't fear another punch in this world.

Bazar Sabir is a lyric poet. The themes of his poems are closely related to the world of feelings, specific features of perception, the scope of the worldview, aspects of the worldview of the lyrical hero of the poem, and humanitarian norms. The subjective nature and validity of the exciting and thought-provoking lyrics in all genres of Bozor Sabir's poetry are full of originality and objective superiority. In this sense, there are no shortage of psychological and dramatic images in his pictorial poems, scenic and romantic poems. Bozor Sabir's poem mentions the poet's own soul, inner feelings and thoughts towards the working people. In his poems, solutions to social issues are expressed through thoughts, reflections, and philosophical discussions based on history and humanity. The concept and image of the

motherland in the poems of Bazar Sabir is constantly improving with the passage of history and the improvement of the perception and feelings of the lyrical hero.[1.C.123]

I am the father of the motherland
On the face of the eye, if my eyes are ringing.
His grief is like the grief of an orphan,
He ate his bread and tasted his water.
For the country in the battle of Girmon,
I was shot in the womb.
I was born with Girmon's arrow, mother,
The country will not die as I did not die.

The connection between the existence of a person, a nation and a homeland is the ideological content of many of Bozor Sabir's poems ("Mountain", "Red Line", "Home", "A night from the homeland"). In his series of poems dedicated to the theme of the Motherland, the historical view of the lyrical hero occupies a special place. In them, the heroic and tragic pages of the history of the nation and the motherland pass through the feelings and thoughts of the lyrical hero, the dramatic scenes of the life and struggle of the ancestors of the Tajik people and their proud children for freedom. and well-being will appear. Bozor Sabir's series of poems are dedicated to Tajikistan, to our native city, to the mountains of our beloved country ("Tajikistan", "Toglar bagherida", "Dushanbe", "Hasad mebaram"). [3.C.34]

In his poems about famous people of the past and present, the poet emphasized the connection of a person with the people and the motherland through an artistic image ("Firdavsi", "Ainy Yadgorligi", "A piece from the poet", "I love you like Bukhara", "Journey to Hearts", etc. "Bazar Sabir" describes his childhood years, the roads and paths of his hometown, streams and springs, the meeting of his loving Mother, the eyes and confused smile of his beloved, mother He remembered the mountains and tulip fields of his country, the graves of his ancestors and the painful words full of them. "Mohajir" - the main role of the performance was performed by the actors of the State Youth Theater named after Mahmudjon Vahidov, Bozor Sabir The heartache and pain of a patriot is the central theme of the performance "One Night Away from the Homeland". Every poem of Usta Bozor is a performance. Because in the pictorial poem, the situation of the poet is described, a part of his story. However, in the history of our theater, they have rarely created a whole play from scattered poems that attract the audience from the beginning to the end. However, our creator Nozim Melikov, who has a truly poetic nature, was able to find many valuable ideas from the poetry of teacher Bozor Sabir and present it to the audience. The position and status of a person in society, the poet's responsibility to history and humanity, the essence of the author's word in human life, and the goals and tasks form the content of Bozor Sabir's series of poems.[4.C.134]

Be unhappy, be a poet,
Be stubborn, be a poet.
I agree with Saadi Salman,
They imprison me with the sin of poetry.
A crescent rains stones on my lips,
There was poetry in my work.
I wish there was no cure, pain,
Sweet pain, my birth pain.

Bazar Sabir creates traditional forms in the style of free poetry and white poetry.

Bozor Sabir's first poems were published in the Tajik press in the 60s of the 20th century. Author of collections "Payvand" (1972), "Tashbarg" (1974), "Guli Khor" (1978), "Mijgoni Shab" (1981), "Oftobnihol" (1982), "Tashbarg" (1984; in Persian) . , 1990 in Russian), "Taste, Collect" (1987), "Poplar Eye" (1991), "Simhor" (1995), "When I Go Homeland" (1999), "From a Flower. a thorn in a thorn" (2003), "If a poet" (2004), "Blood of the pen" (2010), "Black tulip" (2010). Also, a selection of his poems was published in JIE ("Ustoz Bozor Sabir's selections of poems") in 1995. In Bozor Sabir's poems, the theme of the Motherland is wide and wide. From the father's hut and village to the district, the republic, even the entire Persian-speaking region. He gives colorful verses to the water, soil, and stone that make up the essence of his land. [1.C.167]

Analyzing most of Bazar's poems created in different years, he said that the analytical view and fundamental thinking in his poetry is more descriptive, and he enriches Tajik poetry with unique subtle observations and unexpected colorful scenes. it is possible to come to a conclusion. Muhammadjon Shukurov considers Bozor Sabir's "Special style" as "one of the most interesting events in modern Tajik poetry". This "unique style" is manifested in the creation of poetic images and the use of language. Referring to Bozor's style of expression, Askar Hakimov believes that "the richness of the treasure of his poetic images lies in their novelty and meaningfulness." This critic spoke about Bazar's unique style and called his poetic language interesting from two points of view, both in terms of vocabulary and style. In his opinion, Bazar tries to increase the real content of speech as much as possible, the consistency of words, natural expressions, the language of poetry should be close to the vernacular. This quality is manifested in the style of his poetry, not in the expression of plab folk and spoken words. He strives for simplicity of style, expresses deep meaning and complex impressions in simplicity, the language of his poems is healthy and mature. [3.C.34]

At the borders of the world,
The border of Tajikistan is the Tovich language,
As long as he has a language, he is a patriot.
He has many languages.

In conclusion, there is no doubt about Bazar's place in today's poetry. His poems cannot be read and left aside. His poem is our destiny. His fate is a part of our life. As long as we remember and exist, as long as generations remain, it will accompany us. It is impossible to suppress a word from his speech. His poems dedicated to the Motherland increase our love and affection for the Motherland.

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